

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Predicting health risks from genomic, environmental and lifestyle factors using machine learning

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

Quantitative data of 3 different types will be used:

- **Genomic Data:** Whole genome sequencing (WGS) data, including single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and other genetic variations.
- **Environmental Data:** Information on air quality, water quality, and exposure to various environmental pollutants.
- **Lifestyle Data:** Data on physical activity, diet, smoking status, alcohol consumption, and sleep patterns. WGS raw sequencing data will be in the form of FASTQ files, BAM files and VCF (Variant Call Format). Environmental Data will tabular data stored in CSV, Excel files. Lifestyle Data from surveys will be in CSV or Excel files or proprietary formats from device manufacturers.

II. Standards and metadata

Genomic data will be annotated in accordance with the ENA metadata model. For environmental data, we will follow ISO 19115, a standard for describing geographic information and services, including environmental data. For lifestyle data, we will use HL7 FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources), a standard for exchanging healthcare information electronically, as well as clinical data. The CDISC (Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium) standards will be used for clinical research data.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

Environmental Data on air quality, water quality, and exposure to pollutants will be obtained from governmental and international organisations (e.g., EPA, WHO). New lifestyle and genomic data will be collected from participants.

IV. Secondary use

All raw and analysed data will be made available to researchers for secondary analysis. Participant data will be anonymised to protect identities.

V. Methods for data sharing

All raw data (FASTQ) and processed data generated from WGS experiments will be made available via the public repository, ENA. All environmental and lifestyle-related data will be stored on

platforms such as PANGAEA, and Lifestyle Data will be shared via Zenodo. Analysis pipelines (e.g. Jupyter notebooks) will also be made available on Zenodo. Machine Learning models will be shared on public platforms (e.g. GitHub or HuggingFace), where each model will be assigned a DOI.

VI. Proprietary data

No restrictions will be placed on the data. All participant information will be appropriately anonymised/encrypted in accordance with the GDPR laws.

VII. Timeframes

All data will be released immediately after the publication of the paper.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

SNPs identified from WGS will be saved as VCF (Variant Call Format). Environmental Data will be tabular data stored in CSV, Excel. Lifestyle Data from surveys will be in CSV or Excel, and data from wearable devices will be in JSON, CSV, or proprietary formats from device manufacturers.